

Thai Teenage Prostitution Online

Authors : Somdech Rungsisawat

Abstract : The purposes of this research are to investigate Thai teens' attitude toward prostitution on the internet, to discover the causes of teenage prostitution and to study the relationship between teenage promiscuity and the causes of teenage prostitution. This study is a mixed research which utilized both qualitative and quantitative approach. The population of this study included teenagers and early adults between 14-21 years old who were studying in high schools, colleges, or universities. A total of 600 respondents was sampled for interviews using a questionnaire, and 48 samples were chosen for an in-depth interview. The findings revealed that the majority of respondents recognized that teenage prostitution on line was real. The reasons for choosing the internet to contact with customers included easy, convenient, safe, and anonymous. Moreover, the internet allowed teen prostitutes to contact customers anywhere and anytime. The correlation showed that promiscuity was related to the trend of teen prostitution. Other factors that contributed to increasing widespread teen prostitution online included their need for quick money to buy luxurious products and to support their extravagant behavior.

Keywords : internet, prostitutes, online, Thai teens

Conference Title : ICEMBIT 2014 : International Conference on Economics, Management of Business, Innovation and Technology

Conference Location : London, United Kingdom

Conference Dates : June 29-30, 2014